

Relationship Between Teachers' Leadership Styles and Students' Academic Achievement

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Abstract

Leadership styles play an important role and position in pedagogical activities and school effectiveness because they play a major role in the learning process. The current study looked at the relationship between teacher leadership styles (including democratic, autocratic, transformational and transactional) and student academic achievement at the university level. Head of the Departments of Social Sciences and Master's degree students made up the study population. Twenty-nine Heads of Departments (HODs) and two hundred and six students from five public sector universities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa were selected through simple random and stratified (proportionate) sampling techniques. Data was collected through a questionnaire, the reliability co-efficient of which was 0.72 and 0.82 for HODs and students respectively. The data collected was analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation and Pearson Correlation. The study results indicate that teacher leadership styles are strongly linked to student academic success.

Key Words:

Teachers' Leadership Styles, Students' academic Achievement

Introduction

Effective leadership of teachers is one of the main measures of academic achievement by students. Sidhu (2001) said that educational institutions are the structured learning centers where teachers and learners are fundamental elements of the teaching-learning process. As a role model the students imitate their teachers. The students' academic success relies upon a teacher's instructional process. Teachers in the teaching-learning process convey information, abilities, and experiences to the learners through different forms. The teaching methods used by the classroom teachers are often called models of instructional leadership.

Efficient leadership in education facilitates an effective organizational environment which promotes and promotes the learning of students as well as the instruction of teachers. The leadership of teachers is concerned not only with the students' academic achievement but also provides them with an atmosphere in which they can improve their overall personality. The leadership styles of teachers will affect the process of teaching-learning and the personality development of the students. The approaches and strategies implemented by educational leaders improve the awareness, expertise, strength, honesty and competency of the students as well as their mental, social and emotional capacity (King, 2002).

Successful leaders in education are also interested in students' curriculum and curriculum, which both contribute to academic success and the overall growth in students. Teacher leadership is also necessary for sustainable development of an effective institution (Cotton, 2003).

Fullan (2005) proposing that teacher leadership is an important skill and skill to instill vision, insight for sound strategic planning and ensure positive student success and community engagement. Educational leadership is a shared duty of the community, for taking initiatives to ensure the effectiveness of the institution and students' academic achievement. Thus, educational institutions provide an environment for genuine learning process which ensures improved academic achievement of the learners (Fuller, Young, Barnett, Hirsch & Byrd, 2007; Leithwood, Sammons, Hopkins & Harris, 2006). Different research studies have provided evidence that teachers' leadership strongly influences students' learning and academic achievement (Marks & Printy, 2003).

Instructional Leaders concentrate on the inspiration of students and direct them to the best path to improve their inner abilities through an efficient teaching-learning process. Leadership of teachers promotes an engaging process that influences student behavior and provides an emotional connection between teachers and students; It means that teacher leadership is a contributing factor to students' higher academic achievement (Bolkan & Goodboy, 2010; De Vries, 2008; Sharma, 2002).

Three primary principles, such as vision, plan and action, can be used to create successful teacher leadership. Leaders need an intuitive vision to change their vision in order for the teaching-learning situation to be effective. A teacher serves as a mentor and takes organizational decisions on instructional quality and academic outcomes for students in the learning process. Leadership of teachers plays a significant role in decision making, as diverse and collaborative activities include teaching and learning processes. Teacher leaders also work closely with their staff members and students to accomplish their goals. In team work, using their skills and experiences, teacher leadership communicates and liaises with their team members to improve students' academic performance (Balse & Phillips, 2010; Smylie, 2010).

Teachers' leadership is rooted in their behavior, experiences, skills and dispositions, all of these are spontaneously applied in the institution context for effectively leading and improving students' achievement in an increasingly complex and diverse context. All this is aimed for bringing positive changes in the behavior of the students. Teacher as a leader thus, aim at providing guidance, implementing plans and motivating students for achieving the desired behavioral objectives. Teachers use cooperative, constructive, transactional and autocratic leadership styles in the teaching-learning process as well as at all managerial levels (Hallinger, 2004; Houser & Frymier, 2009; Plax & Kearney, 2010).

In view of the above context, the study centered on the study of the connection between the leadership of teachers and university student accomplishments.

Literature Review

Leadership is a behavioral trait, ability and skill of individuals that they use to direct others for accomplishing certain tasks or goals. These can vary significantly from the understanding of the leader, rather than style. Comparing and comparing one self-understanding of leadership style with the understanding of other people are very critical as self-perception cannot represent the actual style of leadership. Leading oneself understanding means how to act as a leader and lead others in company towards the objectives of sharing (Glanz, 2002; York-Bar & Duker, 2004). Educational Leaders must have primary and secondary styles of leadership. The leader's behavioral role includes primary leadership to affect other people's actions while the leader uses his / her style according to the evolving situation in secondary leadership. Both members exhibit primary leadership style and secondary styles of leadership. Within the evolving scenario the teacher leadership uses the four fundamental forms of leadership with consensus (Hoadley & Christie, 2009). The practitioners gave the following four basic styles of leadership;

Democratic Leadership

In a democratic or participatory style of leadership, members of the group and followers are encouraged to participate in the decision-making process. Leader shall involve members of the group for the achievement of assigned activity, group discussion, development of self-reliance among them. Research studies of (Chapman, 2011; Goldstein & Noguera, 2006) stated that this style provides guidance, develop consensus and adoption to the prevailing condition. It increases the morale and performance of community members. This means that the style of democracy leadership allows students to engage in the organizational preparation and decision-making process. Education reform and planning empower political officials to work together in favor of public education and build positive relationships. Democratic leadership therefore places emphasis on guiding the work of education and improving the performance of the institution.

Characteristics of Democratic Leadership

- Group members are inspired by free articulation in order to develop a consensus.
- Member of the Group shall be involved in the decision-making process.
- In the group members' self-esteem may be developed.

Transformational Leadership

Masood et al, under The revolutionary leaders (2006) have an impact on their followers to help them fulfill their highest moral goal. This can be achieved through effective administration skills that reinforce emotional connections to their supporters. Transformational leadership turns the leaders and their followers' knowledge and expertise into

high technical abilities and stimulating activities. The leader gives an inspirational motivation to develop the self-esteem of the members of the group. The leader also takes care of the emotions of his/her followers to improve outcomes of the organization. (Davis, Darling-Hammond, LaPointe & Myerson, 2005).

Characteristics of Transformational Leadership

- Leaders give attention to the individual requirements of the group members.
- Leader cares for emotions of the group members.
- Leader develops vision among group members.

Transactional Leadership

Transactional leaders encourage and empower their followers to reward their efforts. Transaction leaders are often influenced by praise, appreciation and reprimand for their followers. The principle of succession between the leader and his followers is preserved in this form of leadership. The system is based on the assumption that the company pays employees. This model is the basis for both the concept of conditional incentives and management. A leader praises the contributions of a community member for completing the tasks; uses enhancement strategies (Bass et al., 2003).

Characteristics of Transactional Leadership

- This style commends the efforts of the followers for the tasks.
- Patiently treat the supporters.
- Give praises and rewards them on efficient performance.

Autocratic Leadership

The autocratic or authoritarian leader is strongly and tightly governed by strict policies. The chief retains hold of the company's supporters directly. The autocratic style of leadership thus controls the decision-making process, sets goals separately, and assigns tasks in accordance with the proposed strategy. Autocratic leaders take note that decision-making procedures are carried out in due time and rigidly (Robinson & Oetinger, 2008).

Characteristics of Autocratic Leadership

- Set goals individually with a little bit or no opinion from the followers.
- Autocratic leaders maintain a strict control on the followers.
- Leader has a dominant role in the decision-making process.

Objectives of the Study

The research objectives were the following.

- Relationship between teachers' leadership styles and students' academic achievement
- Relationship between teachers' democratic, transformational, transactional and autocratic
- and students' academic achievement

Delimitations of the Study

Due to delimited resources, the study includes the five (05) universities in the public sector in Khyber Pakhtunkhawa, the 29 (HODs) and two hundred and six (206) students in the departments concerned, in the selected universities. Universities in the private sector were not subject to this report.

Research Methodology

The research was a cross-sectional survey, and quantitative co-relational design was used to collect data from the respondents.

Population

All heads and master students of the social sciences departments of the public sector universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhawa have been included in the study population.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Through simply random and stratified (proportionate) sampling techniques twenty-nine (29) HODs and two hundred and six (206) students were selected as a sample group for the study.

The data were collected using a questionnaire, consisting of themes underpinning teachers' leadership styles. Items concerning all four major teachers' leadership styles (democratic, autocratic, transformational and transactional) were incorporated in the data collection instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

The questionnaire was pilot tested in Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University Dir Upper on eight HODs and sixty master level students of the social sciences departments. The reliability coefficient value obtained was .72 and .82 for HODs and students respectively. After the pilot testing of the instrument, it was administered to the respondents for final data collection. The collected data were analyzed and interpreted with the help of SPSS version 19 using Mean scores, Standard Deviation and Pearson Correlation.

Data Analysis and Presentation

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation Values of the HODs Responses

Items	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Democratic Leadership Style.	29	2.40	5.00	4.11	.709
Transformational Leadership Style.	29	2.10	5.00	3.88	.923
Transactional Leadership Style.	29	1.80	5.00	3.79	.907
Autocratic Leadership Style.	29	2.20	5.00	3.72	.891
As a whole Leadership Styles	29	2.32	5.00	3.88	.847

Table 1 above displays compositions of the leadership styles of the teachers in the five chosen universities (e.g. egalitarian, dynamic, transactional and autocratic). The democratic leadership style of teachers was the highest average value of 4,11 which indicates that it is highest in four university-level teacher leadership styles. On the other hand, teachers have the lowest mean value of autocratic leadership of 3,72, which indicates the lowest degree of conformity among the four leadership types of teachers.

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation Values of the Students' Responses

Items	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Dev.
Democratic Leadership Style.	206	1.00	5.00	4.01	.982
Transactional Leadership Style.	206	1.00	5.00	3.78	1.045
Autocratic Leadership Style.	206	1.00	5.00	3.77	1.072
whole Leadership Styles	206	1.00	5.00	3.864	1.033

The above table 2 depicts teachers' leadership styles (i.e. democratic, transformational, transactional and autocratic) in five selected universities. Teachers' democratic leadership style was found to have the highest mean value 4.01, which shows that it has the highest level of observance among four teachers' leadership styles at the university level. On the other hand, teachers' autocratic leadership style was found to have the lowest mean value 3.77, which shows that it has the lowest level of observance among four teachers' leadership styles.

Table 3. Relationship between Teachers' Leadership Styles and Students' CGPA Score

Styles & CGPA	Mean Score	Std. Deviation	R	r ²	Sig.
Teachers' leadership styles	3.86	1.033	-0.980	0.960	.000
CGPA	2.67	1.766			

The above table shows that a majority of respondents were of the view that teachers' leadership styles have a significant correlation with students' academic achievement (CGPA). The mean score of teachers' leadership styles were 3.86, standard deviation score 1.033 and students' academic achievement (CGPA) mean score 2.67 and standard deviation value 1.766.

Teachers' leadership styles in the classroom have a strong negative co-relation which is reflected by the Pearson r value -0.980. The effects are shown by the r² value 0.960 which shows that 96% of the students' academic achievement may be influenced by teachers' leadership styles in teaching-learning process.

Table 4. Correlation Matrix of teachers' Leadership Styles and Students' CGPA Score

	CGPA	Democratic	Transformational	Transactional	Autocratic
Democratic					
Pearson Correlation	-0.976**	1			
Sig (2-tailed)	.000				
N	206	206			
Transformational					
Pearson Correlation	-0.976**	0.984**	1		
Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	206		
N	206	206	206		
Transactional					
Pearson Correlation	-0.978**	0.981**	0.992**	1	
Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	206	
N	206	206	206	206	
Autocratic					
Pearson Correlation	-0.971**	0.977**	0.991**	0.997	1
Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	206
N	206	206	206	206	206
Teachers' leadership styles					
Pearson Correlation	-0.980**	0.990**	0.997**	0.996**	0.997**
Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
N	206	206	206	206	206

Correlation Strength: $r \geq 0.70$ = Highest; $0.50 < r < 0.69$ = High; $0.30 < r < 0.49$ = Medium; $r 0.01 \leq 0.29$ = Low;

** The correlation is significant at the level of 0.01 (2-tailed).

Upper figure of the cell = Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)

Lower cell count = P-value

Table 4 shows the correlation between teacher leadership styles and student academic achievement (CGPA). The table shows that all variables have positive correlations with each other with a high value of $P = .000$ and $P = .01$. There's a clear negative link between teacher leadership democratic style and student achievement ($r = -0.976$, $P = .000$), the transformational style of teacher leadership and student achievement ($r = -0.976$, $P = .000$), the transactional style of teacher leadership and student achievement ($r = -0.978$, $P = .000$), the autocratic style of teacher leadership and student achievement ($r = -0.978$, $P = .000$). Similarly, highest correlation has been observed among different styles such as transformational and democratic ($r = 0.984$, $P = .000$), transactional and democratic ($r = 0.981$, $P = .000$), autocratic and democratic ($r = 0.971$, $P = .000$), transformational and transactional ($r = 0.992$, $P = .000$), transformational and autocratic ($r = 0.991$, $P = .000$) and transactional and autocratic teachers' leadership styles ($r = 0.997$, $P = .000$). Teachers' leadership styles have a strong negative significant correlation ($r = -0.980$) with CGPA and having significant positive correlation with democratic ($r = 0.990$), transformational ($r = 0.997$), transactional ($r = 0.997$) and autocratic leadership styles ($r = 0.996$) respectively.

Discussion

The results indicate that the style of teacher democracy was the most common form for university professors in the educational and learning phase that the findings of (Ademilua, 1999) supported. This finding was consistent with the findings of earlier studies (Ige, 2001). A significant negative correlation was found between the autocratic leadership style of teachers and the academic achievement of students. The finding was not consistent with the findings of (Adeyemi, 2011) who found individuals to be working efficiently under the style of autocratic leadership. However, the finding was supported (Akerle, 2007). A significant negative correlation has been found between the style of democratic leadership of teachers and the academic achievement of students. The findings were different from (Akerle, 2007), which showed a strong positive link between the teacher's style of democratic leadership and the students' academic success. Similarly, a significant negative relationship was also found between teachers and academic achievement of students and transformation and transactional leadership styles. The finding was inconsistent with the findings of (Goldring & Sharon, 1993; Liberman, Beverly & Alexander, 1994). Similarly a strong positive correlation was observed within different teachers' leadership styles.

Conclusions

Based on the study findings it is concluded that those university teachers who used the style of democratic leadership

in their teaching were at the highest level, which indicates that it is sufficiently an above average observance level. Given the HODs and students' responses, it is concluded that the selected universities, teachers' transformational, transactional and autocratic leadership styles in the teaching-learning process were on an above average level of observance. It is also concluded that the selected universities teachers did not rely on a single style of leadership but use a composite of these four styles, depending on the requirement and situation of their teaching. The study also concludes that there has been a strong negative correlation between the democratic, transformational, transactional and autocratic styles of teacher leadership and student academic achievement.

Recommendations

It is recommended that university teachers may encourage students for the achievement of tasks, group discussion, cooperative learning and free expression. This may be possible if in-service trainings and refresher courses may be organized for the university's teachers.

It is recommended that the university teachers ought to acknowledge constructive criticism, allocate task for learners, give attention to personal requirements of the students, instill vision among them and make sure active participation in curricular and co-curricular activities. It would be worthwhile for high authorities to organize refresher courses, workshops, symposiums and seminars for university teachers on regular basis.

It is recommended that university teachers may appreciate students' efforts, reprimand them for not achieving the given tasks on time, adopt back up techniques and promote a feed-back mechanism for the students in the form of rewards.

It is recommended that teachers at the university level set goals individually, work according to their plan, achieve tasks on time, assign tasks to students and check them strictly. This may be achievable only if pre-service and in-service training programs are arranged on a regular basis for the university teachers.

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